

EVALUATION OF CHILDREN AND TEENAGERS' PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Ocena aktywności ruchowej dzieci i młodzieży

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Summary

In days of progressive consumption of everyday life apart from professional duties, social, home and scientific, young people need to undertake active forms of intellectual or physical activity. Forms connected with motion activity can contribute to development of interests and personality. Also it can rise sport activity, unload the nervous tension and prevent the civilization diseases. The recreation is the voluntary activity and its forms are the result of type of interests and place of the people living. The activities are undertaken in spare time for rest to improve health and to entertain. They include all forms of activity not only motion and social improvement.

The article presents the results of studies which concern the forms and the ways of spending spare time dedicated to motion recreation, main barriers connected with the motion recreation and costs connected with it. The article represents the children and teenagers' current profile of participation in motion recreation in the theory - verifying way. The studies had on aim opinion of pupils' motion shape from three kinds of schools: elementary school, gymnasium and high school and tested what form of activity are expected by children and teenager's.

Słowa kluczowe: aktywność fizyczna, rekreacja ruchowa, cechy motoryczne.

Streszczenie

W dobie postępującej konsumpcji życia codziennego zaznacza się ogromna potrzeba podejmowania poza obowiązkami zawodowymi, społecznymi, domowymi i nauką, aktywnych form aktywności umysłowej lub fizycznej. Formy związane z aktywnością ruchową mogą przyczynić się do rozwoju zainteresowań i osobowości. Mogą również podwyższać aktywność sportową, rozładowywać napięcia nerwowe oraz zapobiegać chorobom cywilizacyjnym. Rekreacja z założenia jest aktywnością dobrowolną a jej formy wynikają głównie z typu zainteresowań i miejsca pobytu człowieka. Zajęcia podejmowane są w czasie wolnym dla odpoczynku do pomnażania zdrowia, rozrywki i samodoskonalenia. Obejmują one wszystkie formy aktywności, nie tylko ruchowe i aprobowane społecznie.

Opracowanie prezentuje wyniki badań dotyczących m. in. form i sposobów spędzania czasu wolnego, czasu poświęconego na rekreację ruchową, głównych powodów uprawiania rekreacji ruchowej, barier związanych z uprawianiem rekreacji ruchowej oraz wydatków z nią związanych. Artykuł przedstawia aktualną charakterystykę dzieci i młodzieży w świetle uczestnictwa w rekreacji ruchowej w sposób teoretyczno-weryfikacyjny. Badania miały na celu ocenę kondycji ruchowej uczniów trzech rodzajów szkół: podstawowej, gimnazjum i liceum oraz zbadanie jakie formy aktywności są oczekiwane przez dzieci i młodzież.

Introduction

Physical recreation every year has become increasingly popular. Human needs are associated with quality of life related to health, physical fitness and the attainment of those objectives. Selection of the preferred form of physical activity depends largely on the interests and needs of man. The other factors determining such a choice should include the current level of physical fitness, the availability of facilities, financial resources, and how much free time.

The study presents the results of research concerning forms and ways of spending leisure time spent in physical recreation, the main reasons for doing physical recreation, barriers related to the practice of physical recreation and expenses associated with it. The article presents the current characteristics of children and adolescents in the light of participation in physical recreation in a theoretical verification. The study was designed to evaluate physical fitness of students of three types of schools: elementary school, gymnasium and high school, and to investigate what forms of activity are expected by children and teenagers.

Recreation and physical activity in the literature

Recreation comes from the Latin verb Recreo - renew, revive, and is a form of mental or physical activity undertaken outside of their professional duties, social, and domestic science, used to rest and entertainment. It contributes to the development of interests and personality, increase physical activity, the discharge of nervous tension and prevent lifestyle diseases. Recreation is an activity inherently voluntary. Its forms are mainly due to the type of interest and location of man. Activities are undertaken in their free time for rest to multiply health, entertainment and self-improvement, covering all forms of activity, not just movement, socially approved (Great Encyclopedia PWN,

2004, p. 234).

Recreation is characterized with such features as: the activity, voluntariness, selflessness and pleasure. Activities can be:

- passive – such as sunbathing, watching television, listening to music or
- active – with forms of mental effort predominantly: chess, crossword puzzles, and muscular exercise: swimming, mountain walking, playing sports (Toczek-Werner, 2002, p. 11).

Corbin distinguishes between four groups of recreational activities:

1. operational activities - recreational sports, practicing their favors the extension of man's physical fitness,
2. hobbies classes,
3. cultural,
4. mixed activities that sustain the interest of the entity (Demel, Humen, 1970, p.11).

Recreation can be divided into:

1. physical recreation (physical),
2. creative recreation,
3. recreation, culture and entertainment,
4. recreation of social activity (Czajkowski, 1979, p. 76).

Wolanska defines physical recreation as "... to address the content of the physically or sports tourism, which man gives himself willingly in their free time for rest, leisure and personal development" (Wolanska 1989, p. 9).

Education for leisure is a difficult art of permanent, creative act, rich in elements of autonomy, which will result in happiness and satisfaction, enrichment mental life, the personality and ratcheting in the ideological and moral factors, experience of affirmation and joy of life (Czajkowski 1979, p. 100).

Physical culture - besides the material culture and spiritual culture of the society component, which task was to shape the physical development of man and his physical abilities. It is the expression of certain attitudes towards his own body and its needs, conscious and active concern for their development, fitness and health, ability to organize and leisure activities with the greatest benefit of physical and mental health (Barankiewicz 1998, p. 145).

Physical education is understood as the deliberate impact on the whole man, whose purpose is to shape its development and to prepare them for life in society. In other words, that education for active and creative introduction to the world objective human, social achievements, it is the world wide anthropologically understood culture. Furthermore, in the process of education shall also enter into the world of human nature, but nature humanized. (Krawczyk 1995, p.54).

The concept of "sport for all" internationally recognized, was introduced into the world of sports in 1966 by the Council of Europe. The concept of "sport for all" is completely different from the understanding of sport in the traditional manner. Wolanska "... the term encompasses not only the different sports disciplines, but also various forms of physical activity is spontaneous, unstructured games involving physical movement to organized physical activity regularly performed" (Toczek-Werner, 2002, p. 12).

The objectives of physical education can be formulated as follows:

comprehensive and harmonious development, health, and multiplying the specific increase in physical and immunization of the organism to the harmful physical and mental stimuli, shaping the student a sense of responsibility for their development, health and that of others, physical fitness, and to form the need for continuous action to preserve these values, awakening of interest in various forms of physical activity for recreational, sports and tourism, outfit in the specific knowledge and skills enabling him to actively participate in these forms of movement (Bielski, 2005, p. 40-42).

The degree of mobility in each man is different and depends on many factors, such as physiological or psychological. Seeking to this trait, and the ability to assess the scale of 1-5, while a man is extremely sluggish (hipokinetic), and 5, a child who can not sit still any longer (hyperkinetic). Both the first and the second case, there is a problem with these children in physical education classes. Hyperkinetic children are more active, but casually learn new steps and quickly lose interest in them. In the case of children, hipokinetic, it is appropriate to motivate you to move, and then learn how to accurately and sometimes they are more efficient than hyperactive children. Today is characterized by the capacity of distinguishing human liveliness and coordination. For fitness include strength, endurance and speed of motion and coordination abilities to control and regulation of movements and the ability to motor learning (Czabanski 2000, p. 31-32).

Shaping of motor skills of children and youth in the process of physical exercise is characterized by a close relationship with the psychological development of students. In shaping the motor features should not be reduced teaching interactions - education only to the quantitative burden of the body, using the specified standard practice, but in parallel to develop psychological traits. This means that we are operating in the process of teaching the concept of psychomotor development, rather, not - only the motor. It is therefore assumed that the process of shaping of motor skills, teachers should expose the first of these forms of physical activity that require the involvement of student awareness.

The methodology of development of motor skills of children and teenagers' there are two, closely interrelated, and the plane impacts and teaching - educational:

selecting and applying measures appropriate to the age, sex and individual potential of students, transfer students information on the impact of exercise and movement forms task force for the development of the organism (Denisiuk, Badory, Botwinski 1980, p. 24).

The development of human motor skills after the best period of learning is a more or less disturbed by the course of the process of puberty.

Occurring disturbances and impaired motor skills rely on the general disorder of motor skills, agility, decrease, decreasing the accuracy, new forms of physical extravagance, disturbance dynamics, lower the motor abilities and frequent contradictions in the overall behavior of the motor (Meinel 1967, p. 354-355).

We can promote physical activity for children and teenagers' for:

- Physical activity should be increased by reducing sedentary time (e.g., watching television, playing computer video games or talking on the phone).
- Physical activity should be fun for children and teenagers'.
- Parents should try to be role models for active lifestyles and provide children with opportunities for increased physical activity.

Physical inactivity is a major risk factor for developing coronary artery disease. It also increases the risk of stroke and such other major cardiovascular risk factors as obesity, high blood pressure, low HDL ("good") cholesterol and diabetes. The American Heart Association recommends that children and adolescents participate in at least 60 minutes of moderate to vigorous physical activity every day. The American Heart Association recommends:

1. All children age 2 and older should participate in at least 30 minutes of enjoyable, moderate-intensity physical activities every day that are developmentally appropriate and varied.
2. If your child or children don't have a full 30-minute activity break each day, try to provide at least two 15-minute periods or three 10-minute periods in which they can engage in vigorous activities appropriate to their age, gender and stage of physical and emotional development.

Children's Need for Physical Activity: Fact Sheet:

- Children today are less fit than they were a generation ago. Many are showing early signs of cardiovascular risk factors such as physical inactivity, excess weight, higher blood cholesterol and cigarette smoking.
- Inactive children, when compared with active children, weigh more, have higher blood pressure and lower levels of heart-protective high-density lipoproteins (HDL cholesterol).
- Even though heart attack and stroke are rare in children, evidence shows that the process leading to those conditions begins in childhood.
- A fitness testing program sponsored by the Chrysler Fund Amateur Athletic Union, which tracks fitness among 9.7 million people between ages 6–17, shows that children are getting slower in endurance running and weaker.
- The National Health and Nutrition Examination Study (NHANES, 1999–2004) found that the prevalence of overweight American adolescents ages 12–19 was 17.9% for males and 16.0 percent for females. There was an increase of nearly 179% from 1971 to 2004.
- About 10% of youth ages 12–19 have total cholesterol levels exceeding 200 mg/dL.
- An estimated 59% of American children under ages 4–11 are exposed to secondhand smoke in the home. An estimated 1,500 American young people become smokers every day.
- 37.2% of high school students spend three or more hours a day watching TV.
- Inactive children are more likely to become inactive adults.
- Healthy lifestyle training should start in childhood to promote improved cardiovascular health in adult life. The following good health practices should be promoted among children:
 - regular physical activity,
 - a low-saturated-fat, low-cholesterol diet after age 2,
 - smoking prevention,
 - appropriate weight for height,
 - regular pediatric medical checkups (American Heart Association, www.americanheart.org 31.10.2010).

Forms of recreation

Recreation, as a team of human behavior is primarily purposeful, conscious activity, which constitutes the content of a dimension of free time. Activity which includes individual and team performance of activities bringing relaxation, entertainment, fitness, health, developing the personality that uses movement as a means to act upon the body depending on the needs of the individual interests, we call recreational physical activity and the behavior of this type are recreational physical activities (Toczek -Werner, 2002, p. 21).

Participants are looking for recreation such forms, which can be characterized by features:

- ease of learning - learning to control and organize,
- the possibility of all-terrain - artificial and natural,
- flexibility in applying rules and policies,
- accessibility for all - for individuals, groups of homogeneous and heterogeneous,

- versatility - full impact on the human body and personality,
- attractiveness carrying behind element of novelty, always positive emotions.
Physical recreation can share because of the intensity of effort in:
- relaxation (walking, fishing, wildlife observation, hobby classes, fun escort),
- an average of intense (recreational motion games, ice skating, sailing, drilling),
- intensive (cross-conditioning, aerobics, swimming distance).
Due to the difficulties (technical complexity), physical recreation is divided into:
- easy (running, cycling, games and movement),
- simple average (volleyball, swimming, ice skating),
- difficult (skiing, windsurfing, climbing, tennis).
Physical recreation can be divided due to the time of the year:
- summer (swimming, fishing, diving, water skiing),
- winter (skiing, skating, sleigh rides, snowboarding),
- all year season (Toczek-Werner, 2002, p. 21).

In carrying out the tasks arising from the concept of recreation should be sought to take into account the rights of children and youth development, tracking trends and processes of acceleration and a better understanding of the factors that intensified to health and development of the human individual. Presented the development stages of physical activity of children and youth are an attempt to do.

Phase I – Preparation (age 3-5):

Tasks: improving the accuracy of the exercise of natural movements, learning new motor skills. There Developing intellectual and peer behavior. Shaping of motor skills.

1. Exercises for disciplines.
2. Improving how to perform basic motor actions (walking, running, jump, throw, grip, overhangs, overcome obstacles, rolling, revolutions, etc.).

- Learning children of new motor skills.
- Shaping motor features such as speed, strength, endurance.
- Developing intellectual children using specially selected games and exercises.
- Shaping skills in the classroom behavior in complex and unusual situations.

Phase II – The general development of (age 7-11):

Tasks: a comprehensive skill development, physical fitness and physical condition. Teaching basic skills, techniques and rules of common sports. There developing the intellectual foundation for social development and self-discipline.

- Exercises for disciplines.
- The physical fitness.
- Developing and improvement of motor coordination.
- Learning techniques and foundations of tactics and psychological resilience.
- Shaping physical strength and mental resilience.
- Learning basic motor skills.
- Exercises in groups of sports-related development of interest in sports.
- Exercises relaxing - concentration.
- Invite with the provisions of the universal sport.
- Learning games and craft.
- Hiking tourism, cycling and water tourism.
- Learning marching songs.
- Shaping skills behavior after the victory and defeat.
- Improving sense of rhythm in the dancing.
- Shaping ability to behave in complex and unusual situations in the classroom.
- Participating in developing moral and ethical traits with specific attention to the ability to cooperate and design sympathetic to other people.

Phase III – development targets (age 11-15):

Objectives: further development of the physical improvement of basic motor skills, techniques, general sports. Shaping social attitudes and internal disciplines.

- Exercises for cleaning - disciplines.
- The physical fitness.
- Improving known exercises, motor skills and techniques for selected sports.
- Exercises relax - focus.
- Improving sense of rhythm in the dance, exercises to music.
- Learning popular marching songs, and improving regional and national.
- Shaping physical strength and mental resilience.
- Participation in achieving the objectives and tasks of health education.
- Learning self-organization of tourist trips.
- Developing moral qualities - ethics, with particular emphasis on the skills of cooperation and friendly attitude

to other people.

➤ Shaping classroom behavior skills in a complex and unusual situations.

Stage IV specialist (age 16-18):

Objectives: to improve physical fitness, basic motor skills, techniques and tactics chosen sport. Self-organization of tourist trips, occupations and skills and conducting classes. Systematic training in line with the interests, sports and tourism. Knowledge of the basic issues of health education. Shape the attitudes of the intended social and internal discipline by:

- Exercises for cleaning disciplines.
- Improving techniques and tactics chosen sport.
- Improving physical fitness.
- Developing skills training in special-interest groups.
- Shaping incentive to the systematic physical ego.
- Improving skills behavior after the victory and defeat,
- Exercises relax - focus.
- Improving sense of rhythm.
- Learning independent organization of tourist trips.
- Shaping classroom behavior skills in a complex and unusual situations.
- Participating in achieving the objectives and tasks of health education.
- Learning independent organization of professions of teaching, judging, the theoretical basis of physical culture.
- Participating in developing moral and ethical objectives with emphasis on the skills of cooperation and friendly attitude to other people (Chrominski 1987, p. 90-93).

One of the most characteristic and fundamental ways to promote both physical recreation are recreational events. It is a form of meeting participants a single, or having completed a cyclical nature of the programming content, sports, recreation, tourism and cultural entertainment.

Each party is subject to a recreational classification includes the following benchmarks:

- place of the event - Outdoor (sport, parks) or in enclosed spaces (gymnasiums, community centers),
- duration of the event - one day or several days,
- cyclical - one-off, occasional or repetitive,
- the scale of activities and number of participants - the massive or small chamber,
- the nature of participation - open or closed,
- the range of content – one-discipline or multidisciplinary,
- a form of organization - festivals, spartakiada, tournaments, leagues.

The most common forms of recreational events are:

- Recreational Festival - is a multidisciplinary public events, which dominate the competition for traditional medium-scale problems usually associated with the specificity of the local environment. The program usually consists of elements of recreational games and port security, fitness tests, racing and fun.
- spartakiada - characterized by a diversity of recreational competition played during the one-off meetings held after the heats or the preparatory period. They are designed for people with higher fitness levels, or were ready for this type of rivalry.
- tournaments ,
- recreation League,
- competitions.

Motives of physical activity

Winiarski has identified seven types of persons engaged in physical recreation:

Type I (activity - hedonistic). This person, in which activity arises from the need of biological motion is pleasant and attractive in itself and has a value autotelic.

Type II (relax). These are people for whom recreation is a form of escape from daily responsibilities and problems, serving mainly leisure and relieve stress and psychological tensions.

Type III (health - hygiene). These are people who practice exercises to improve, maintain health, fitness, figure, beauty, well-being, for the value they are ready to sacrifice for the work of their own bodies (the diet).

Type IV (social - friendly). To those seeking recreation opportunities in social networking, preferring to group forms of leisure.

Type V (seeker of adventure.) These are people who practice forms of recreation supply and emotions associated with risk, gambling, aesthetic experiences, the struggle against the forces of nature, the enemy, himself and his own weakness.

Type VI (ambitious). These are people who seek opportunities in recreation and appreciation to verify, for example, by victory in competitive sports, engaging in leisure activities often receive applause for showing social.

Type VII (cognitive - educational). Includes persons for whom leisure is an opportunity to know and learn something new, a way of self-improvement and development of their interests and tastes (Gracz, Sankowski 2001, p. 124).

The importance of recreation and physical activity in people's lives

Recreation is a process which leads to changes induced by removal work, which weakens the body's functional status (Gracz, Sankowski 2001, p. 115).

The importance of recreation in modern life, with rising risks: noise, fast rhythm of life in deteriorating hygiene: sedentary lifestyle, work, rest, lack of sporting activity, fatigue, substance abuse (Toczek-Werner, 2002, p. 15).

Social importance of recreation and tourism:

- Recreation and tourism are all factors that facilitate the socialization of man, namely the acquisition of its features to help in adjusting to the norms, rules and standards of social behavior desired and acceptable.
- Recreation and tourism are the instruments of human communication. Contacts in the formal or informal group of recreational or tourist permit the exchange of views, information flow, thus providing an effective means of shaping the attitudes of valuable human being.
- Recreation and tourism are the factors of integrating human groups, and interactive processes that affect the level of individual personality, peer groups and local communities.
- Recreation and tourism are all democratic factors human societies. This is a leveling of social differences between people.
 - Recreation and tourism under favorable conditions are an attractive means of social therapy and social reintegration, affecting the individual educationally unsuitable for the social environment (Toczek-Werner, 2002, p. 18).

Movement stimulates the physical development, motor, functional and psychological. The effect of physical activity is optimal to maintain a high level of health and behavior patterns in the developmental process, especially in the circulatory system (Ďuriček, Obodynski 2006, p. 57).

Systematic recreational activity improves mood, the resistance of the nervous system, calms, increases life satisfaction has a positive impact on human mental functioning, and strengthens the capacity of the organism (Gracz, Sankowski 2001, p. 183).

Proven studies show that insufficient physical activity may promote obesity and its treatment to impede, impair coronary circulation and peripheral blood circulation, weakened tendons, muscles, coordination, decreased muscle strength, increase the risk of joint damage and reduce the resistance to the hardships of everyday life (Ďuriček, Obodynski 2006, p. 60).

Barriers in the practice of physical recreation

Dissemination of recreation in society faces several subjective and objective obstacles called barriers that hinder or prevent the physically active leisure.

- Cognitive barriers arise mainly from the universal ignorance of the importance of movement for health and efficient bio-psychosocial functioning of the body.
- Psychological barriers are the consequence of poorly aroused in individuals needs, habits, disposition, lack of sustained motivation which cause mental energy necessary to take the motor activity. These barriers also stem from the lack shaped skills, active use of leisure time, fear of injury or ridicule.
- Cultural barriers due to family traditions and environmental passive recreation, lack of physical activity-friendly designs. Model a lifestyle in which physical recreation is inscribed only in Poland is beginning to spread.
- Ideological barriers associated with the wrong policy, with underestimation of physical recreation as an important component of physical culture. We continue to prefer a professional sport which involves the financial preferences.
- Economic barriers are related to the level of living, rising costs of sports and tourism. Economic conditions limit participation in particular forms that require the use of recreational facilities and sports facilities or leisure.

The importance of rational recreation, and the share of physical activity is widely accepted. In our society, social practice has shown that physical activity is steadily declining. This applies to both adults and children. Most of the adult population (approximately 90%) have sporadic contact with physical culture. Many barriers to broad social context, linked to a lack of good theoretical concepts and patterns that exist in social practice. Overcoming these obstacles is a task for the organizer of today's recreational activity - tourism.

Barriers in the practice of recreation Wolanska include:

- lack of free time,
- lack of adequate psychological characteristics,
- economic constraints,
- negligence, cultural,
- poor motor skills,
- low self-assessment of health
- environmental regulation.

These barriers do not occur in isolation. The problem of education for recreation should take into account the particular period of childhood and the experiences associated with physical activity, which may bear fruit in the future (Gracz, Sankowski 2001, p. 251).

Ways to remove barriers to recreational activity:

- Avoidance of monotony in organizing and conducting classes. Attractive opportunities tailored to the level of exercise is an incentive for their continuation in the future without resistance and prejudices.
- Preventing excessive automate this especially applies in the workplace, threatening and psychological effects of addiction hipokinetic (computers).
- Actively shaping healthy attitudes (especially my attitude instructor).
- Combating stubbornness, a sense of joy and satisfaction.
- Focus on utilitarian and hedonistic values (the pursuit of satisfaction), (Gracz, Sankowski 2001, p. 260).

Purpose, scope and research methodology

To present the current characteristics of children and teenagers' in the light of participation in physical recreation in a theoretical verification. The empirical research conducted aimed at:

- examining the physical activity self-esteem among children and teenagers',
- the time spent on the practice of physical activity,
- knowing the reason for which is cultivated physical recreation,
- identification of problems associated with the practice of physical activity,
- an assessment of the expenditure related to the practice of physical recreation,
- identify the forms of activity, which is missing for children and teenagers'.

For the purposes of the survey was conducted in which we used the method of diagnostic survey, carried out the direct interview technique. The research tool was a questionnaire containing ten questions on issues of physical recreation, and three questions about sex, type of school and place of residence. The questions included the following: self-assessment of physical activity, time, time spent on the practice of physical activity, the reason for which such activity is grown and the problems associated with her practicing.

The study was conducted during the winter among 100 students of the following schools:

- Elementary School, Class VI - 21 people
- Gymnasium, two Class III - 50 people
- High School, Class III - 29 people.

Test results and discussion

The results have been developed in Microsoft Office Excel and presented in graphical form.

Figure 1. Characteristics of respondents

Source: own research.

In this study took part 100 people: 43 girls – 10% children from elementary school, 20% from gymnasium and 13% from high school and 57 boys – 11% from elementary school, 30% from gymnasium and 16% from high school. Most respondents lived in urban areas (85%), of which the largest group was students from gymnasium. Only 15% of respondents came from rural areas, among which is the highest percentage of high school students (13%).

Table 1 Characteristics of respondents

Feature		Elementary school	Gymnasium	High school
Sex	woman	10%	20%	13%
	men	11%	30%	16%
Type of school	Elementary school	21%		
	Gymnasium		50%	
	High school			29%
Place of residence	city	20%	49%	16%
	village	1%	1%	13%

Source: own research.

Figure 2. Forms of leisure activities

Source: own research.

Among the larger group of students spending their free time actively (total 73%), of which elementary school students accounted for 18%, gymnasium - 32% and high school students - 23%. Unfortunately, quite a large percentage of respondents (27%) admitted to passive forms of spending his free time, among which there were 3% of pupils from elementary school, 18% from gymnasium and 6% students from high school.

Figure 3. Assessment of physical activity

Source: own research.

Most respondents rated their physical activity well (43%) and very good (38%). Sufficiently appreciated by 17% of the students, and insufficiently only 2% students from gymnasium.

Children from elementary school assessed their physical activity in the following way: very good - 7%, well - 11%, enough - 3% and none of the children are not marked "unsatisfactory".

Among middle school students in a group of very good and good physical activity responses were divided into equal interest to 19%. Has issued its assessment of adequate physical activity 10% of a group of junior from gymnasium and 2% of them issued a failing grade.

A similar distribution of responses was observed among high school students (very good - 12% good - 13%, enough - 4%). Fail not noted any respondents from high school.

Figure 4. Amount of time spent on leisure per week

Source: own research.

Most students (48%) for physical recreation during the week devoted a to 5 hours. Only 7% of those surveyed responded that they do not devote time for physical recreation. 31% of respondents reported use 5 - 10 hours of physical recreation, and 14% paid the recreation more than 10 hours per week.

Most pupils from elementary school (12%), participating in the study, considered that the physical activities devoted to 5 hours, 5% of respondents with this kind of school is paid from 5 to 10 hours, while most of the time - more than 10 hours spent 4% of the youngest respondents. Very optimistic is the fact that all elementary school children spend in leisure time occupations movement.

Among students from gymnasium, 21% of people said they use free time for physical activities up to 5 hours a week, 17% felt that this is the time interval 5-10 hours, 7% of students said they spent more than 10 hours of physical recreation. In this age group occurred 5% of people who do not their time on leisure mobility, which can be disturbing trailer problem that can have health consequences for the proper functioning of the body.

Percentage distribution of answers given by high school students was similar to the response to their younger colleagues: most respondents (15%) marked the response to 5 hours., Then the 9% spent on leisure physical 5 -10 hours, 3% over 10 hours per week and 2% of high school students they do not devote their time to leisure.

Figure 5. When you practice most professions related to physical recreation?

Source: own research.

Most respondents (70%) said the practice of recreation throughout the week, of which 16% are elementary school pupils, 33% - students from gymnasium and 21% students from high school. Weekend physical activity cultivated 30% of respondents, which accounted for 5% of students from elementary school, 17% of respondents from gymnasium and 8% of high school students.

Figure 6. Reasons for practicing recreation

Source: own research.

The main reason for doing physical recreation for children and young people is physical - a total of 30% followed by: a pretty figure - 27%. It was only in third place respondents ticked health - 15%, suggesting a relatively low awareness of the impact of active leisure activities on health.

In this regard, it appears appropriate to educate children and youth in order to present the consequences of the lack of movement for the proper functioning of the body, which in light of the obesity society becomes extremely important issue. Some students (13%) take a common recreational activity for relaxation. For some (10%) proved to be an important reason for social contacts concluded during sports movement. Few respondents (4%), physical recreation grow because of the possibility relieve stress, and for one student from high school reason was a hobby.

Figure 7. Practicing forms of recreation

Source: own research.

The most common declared by children and teenagers', physical activity was a form of jogging and cycling (respectively 19% response rate). In third place was the football (14%), of which most definitely were interested in this form of students from gymnasium. In the order of the respondents highlighted the activities at the swimming pool - 13%, volleyball and fitness for 9% of respondents. 9% of respondents from gymnasium in response to others as physical activity, which usually do: walking – 3%, parkour – 3 %, dancing – 1 % and kick boxing – 1%. One high school student confessed to horseback riding.

Figure 8. Problems related to the practice of physical activity

Source: own research.

Most respondents (65%) had no problems related to the practice of physical activity (30% from gymnasium, 20% students from high school and 15% students from elementary school). Among the most problems highlighted by respondents was a no motivation (14%: 11% gymnasialist and 3% students from high school), no free time (8%: 4% students from high school, and 2% from gymnasium and pupils from elementary school) and ashamed before the others (7 %: 3% students from gymnasium and elementary school and 1% students from high school). For 5% of respondents had a disease problem, but only for one school boy had not money.

Figure 9. Forms of physical activity

Source: own research.

Most respondents (36%) performed its physical activity at school activities, among which were: 7% of pupils from elementary school, 17% from gymnasium and 12% from high school. Classes attended school 35% of children and teenagers: 8% from elementary school, 13% from gymnasium and 14% students from high school. With parents and family for physical recreation grows 16% of respondents: 4% of children from elementary school, 11% young people from gymnasium and only 1% students from high school. Only 13% of respondents reported the practice of physical activity in a sports club, of which 2% were students from elementary school, 9% from gymnasium and 2% from high school.

Figure 10. Monthly expenditure on leisure physical

Source: own research.

Most of the children and teenagers' (68%) benefited from the free classes: 13% of students from elementary school, 34% of high school and 21% of high school. Expenditure of up to 50 Polish zloty monthly reported 19% of respondents (4% students from elementary school, 11% from gymnasium and 4% from high school). After 4% of respondents from each group identified its expenses related to the practice of recreation ranging from 50 to 100 Polish zloty per month. Only one student from the school declared the expenses of 100 - 200 Polish zloty per month.

The results also show a powerful free realization of physical activity. One can only hope that organized activities are very popular among children and teenagers' from different backgrounds, both urban and rural areas.

Figure 11. What forms of activity are missing in the offer recreational facilities

Source: own research.

More than half of respondents (52%) did not feel the lack of any form of activity in the range of recreational facilities. The main place where children and teenagers' were missing (24%) had year-round ice rink, which could play and practice skating or playing hockey. No skate park where he could have been practicing professionally run and jump on the rolls found 9% of respondents. For 7% of the students lacked the slopes where you would ride a snowboard. A small group (3%) would like to be able to use the courts for squash, the 2% of respondents were interested in off-road riding on quads and shooting.

Conclusions

Results of this study indicated a high physical activity among children and teenagers' from three types of schools: elementary, gymnasium and high school. Marked the correct trend and it is hoped that it will be maintained or increased, and the children and teenagers' will increasingly be concerned with active forms of leisure.

Our results showed a very good self-esteem of physical activity among the respondents. Although they spend part of their free time in a passive way, it assessed its activity well or very well. Such assessments may indicate a misunderstanding of the concept of children and teenagers' physical activity.

The main reasons for practicing physical recreation among the respondents are: physical fitness, nice figure and health. The positive result in children and teenagers' will be the pursuit of its objective, and this motion may be accompanied by them throughout life.

Studies have shown that the most cultivated forms of physical activity are running, cycling, football and classes at the pool. Expansion of bicycle paths will positively affect the prevalence of cycling and encouraged to engage in this activity.

Optimistic is the fact that most respondents did not see any problems related to the practice of physical activity. Most children and teenagers' realised physical activity at school and extracurricular activities that were free of charge. It turned out that this is a very good form of recreation use, bringing many benefits to participants and exempting from the payment of fees.

Year-round ice rink, ski, skate park, a designated route for quads or range help in developing its activity for a large group of surveyed children and teenagers'. Separate place would be safer than driving on the benches or low walls in the city center, close to busy streets, which in many cases takes place at the moment.

The results obtained can form the basis of research knowledge for those responsible for organizing sports and recreational activities. There are several forms of physical activity, which could be organized and that their organization does not require many financial resources. It is hoped that in the near future, created more opportunities for active leisure time.

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